

Reconstructing Multiple Injuries through Osteobiography: A Case Study from Italy

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ABSTRACT This investigation aims to underscore the value of an osteobiographical approach that focuses on understanding the interactions between status, medical treatments, and disability. This article presents the interpretation of a multitrauma case within an archaeological framework. The site of Selvicciola, dated between the first half of the fourth century C.E. and the beginning of the eighth century C.E., with its Roman *villa rustica* and a cemetery with a church, provides the background context for this study. The individual (T90/5) has been selected from the funerary area for this investigation. During his life, T90/5 experienced several injuries. He received care and rehabilitation but died within weeks from a femoral neck fracture.

Keywords: bioarchaeology; disability; Late Antique; medical treatment; Selvicciola

Questa indagine si propone di valorizzare un approccio osteobiografico che esplora le interazioni tra stato sociale, trattamenti medici e disabilità. L'articolo presenta l'interpretazione di un caso di multi-trauma all'interno di un contesto archeologico proveniente dal sito di Selvicciola. L'area archeologica, datata alla prima metà del IV secolo d.C. con continuità d'uso fino all'VIII secolo d.C., include una villa rustica romana e un cimitero con una chiesa. L'individuo al centro di questa indagine (T90/5), rinvenuto nell'area cimiteriale, subì durante la sua vita diversi traumi fisici, ricevendo dalla comunità cure e riabilitazione. Morì poche settimane dopo la frattura del collo del femore.

Parole chiave: bioarcheologia; disabilità; Tarda Antichità; trattamenti medici; Selvicciola

Introduction

Understanding the nature of trauma experienced by members of archaeological communities has long been a topic of interest in bioarchaeological research (Baker 2025; Martin and Harrod 2015; Paine et al. 2007; Redfern and Roberts 2019; Sala et al. 2019). This investigation, including determining the cause and effect of these episodes, is critical in paleopathology and forensic sciences (Knüsel and Smith 2013; Kranioti 2015; Kranioti et al. 2019; Lovell 1997). The current

literature in forensic pathology and bioarchaeology provides methodologies and protocols for investigating the nature of bone injuries, as well as the processes associated with their formation (Cattaneo et al. 2017; Knüsel and Smith 2013; Redfern and Roberts 2019 and literature therein). Bone calluses from healed fractures are easily detectable on dried remains. Injuries might be accidental or intentional outcomes of violent processes (Klaus 2018; Mitchell 2012). Trauma may be indicated by a single acute incident (evident in the skeleton as antemortem or

perimortem trauma) or by repeated injuries (multiple antemortem traumas or a combination of antemortem and perimortem trauma; Mant et al. 2020:586). However, when multiple traumas are observed on skeletons, the discrimination between multiple and single injury events with multiple fractures is challenging (Gowland 2016; Judd 2002). In bioarchaeology, determining the total episodes of multiple fractures is generally not feasible due to the remodeling of fracture calluses. Consequently, researchers rely on the total fractures per individual to assess recidivism via clinical diagnosis (e.g., Antunes-Ferreira et al. 2020; Kozakaitė et al. 2018). Additionally, soft tissue injuries are not visible, likely leading to underestimating injury frequency (Mant 2019).

An injury recidivist can be defined as an individual who experiences repeated trauma, a pattern considered a chronic condition (Sledjeski et al. 2008), and who may have been treated for two or more distinct injuries (Williams et al. 1997). Recent clinical and paleopathological studies indicate a link between trauma, psychological stress, and an increased risk of fractures (Al-Ani et al. 2010; Mant et al. 2021; Möller et al. 2009; Pedersen et al. 2016; Yu et al. 2012). Bohling et al. (2022:78, Table 3; *Bioarchaeology of Disability, BoD*) categorize physical impairment duration as “End of life,” “Acquired: medium to long term,” “Acquired: significant skeletal alterations,” and “Congenital.” In contrast, Tilley and Cameron (2012; *Bioarchaeology of Care, BoC*) define care duration as short (less than three months), medium (three to six months), or long (more than six months). Trauma leading to socially constructed disability resulting from physical impairment can have significant implications for both the individual and the community in terms of time, effort, and resources required for healing and long-term care. This assessment underscores the necessity of considering diverse adaptive strategies for chronic illness or disability. In an archaeological context, surviving trauma may be reflected in tangible osteological evidence that reveals physical impairments impacting an individual’s life. The embodiment of the injury encompasses not only the physical events causing it but also the dimension of disability (Bohling et al. 2022; Tilley 2015).

This article presents a case study of multiple traumatic incidents observed on the skeleton of an adult male buried in a cemetery dated between the beginning of the fourth and eighth centuries C.E. (Incitti 1997; Micarelli 2020). The final goal is to examine what happens when an individual requires care more than once. The complexities of assessing the timing and causes of multiple injuries in skeletal remains, as well as examining traumas and intentional care/treatment, will be addressed. Tilley (2015:96–118)

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argues that cultural healing practices in past communities are intricate, dialectical, and highly contextual. As stated by Yaussy (2021) for intersectional investigation, this research considers which intersection matters the most for the research question, the fracture pattern.

The Multiple Trauma Case Study: Historical and Archaeological Background

Background to medical knowledge of orthopedic treatments in classical and post-classical times

The sophisticated level of medical knowledge during the Imperial period of Rome has been widely recognized (Gazzaniga 1990). From the first to third centuries C.E., three different cultural developments consolidate advanced medical practices among the Romans. First, establishing the *scholae medicorum* (schools of doctors), promoted by Augustus and later by following emperors, was critical in producing expert medical practitioners. Many of the early doctors in Rome were from Greece or trained in Greece (among them Galen of Pergamon, whose views on anatomy and theory of the four humors dominated Western medical science for more than 1,300 years; Jackson 2005). The origins of the Roman medical culture can be traced back to the Greek Hippocratic doctrines guiding the medical assessment of patients (Gazzaniga and Marinozzi 2014). The *scholae medicorum* were very effective in producing skilled medical practitioners; Pliny the Elder pointed out that medical specialists in Rome were so numerous that an ill person could easily find a specialist for any health problem (*Naturalis Historiae*, 29, 5.11, as underlined in Stambaugh 1988). Second, with the expansion of the Roman Empire, professional military medical practitioners were educated on how to treat war casualties. These specialists advanced their skills along the frontlines of battle; they developed expertise in orthopedics, which improved recovery rates (Gazzaniga and Marinozzi 2014; Santacroce et al. 2017). Treatment of fractures and dislocations (including methods of traction for reducing fractures of the long bones) became one of the main foci of Roman medicine (Baker 2004; Ponseti 1991). Finally, treatises of key importance for the history of medicine, such as those contained in *De medicina* (*About Medicine*) by Aulus Cornelius Celsus and Galen’s corpus of textbooks, started to circulate widely in Roman territories (Cosmacini and Menghi 2012). These documents were shared extensively, guiding medical practitioners as they aided injured individuals (Gosbell 2018). The placement of medical buildings dedicated

to sharing knowledge of medicine, for example, the *Schola Medicorum*, found next to the temple of Minerva Medica on the Esquiline hill in Rome (Zucconi 2019), confirms the importance and value of this discipline among the Romans.

The use and development of medical instruments to treat injured individuals also offer direct evidence for medical practices. Among them, the *skolopomachairon* was suitable for severing bones and vertebrae, the *mochlikos* was useful for lifting fractured bone fragments, and the *prion* was used to perform amputations (Gazzaniga and Marinozzi 2014:246). The discovery of these instruments by archaeologists and the description of them by Roman authors provide insight into their uses (Gazzaniga and Marinozzi 2014). Archaeologists have found that the tools used in Roman medicine look similar to instruments designed as carpentry utensils. Fortunately, discovering medical devices in situ at the sites of Herculaneum and Pompeii provides this critical context (Jackson 2005:99, 102). Medical utensils found at the sites of Herculaneum and Pompeii, as well as at the site of Eutyches's "Surgeon's House" in Rimini, are well-known examples of surgical instruments recovered in situ (Gazzaniga and Marinozzi 2014; Jackson 2009). Additionally, one-third of the surgical instruments recovered from the Rimini surgeon's site were associated with orthopedic medical practices (Jackson 2009). This discovery provides valuable insight into medical knowledge during this period. Archaeological and literary evidence is confirmed by the large number of paleopathological studies that illustrate examples of health problems among Roman citizens (e.g., Gilmour et al. 2019; Lovell 2016; Minozzi et al. 2012; Redfern 2010). For example, a preadult recovered in Herculaneum with a wooden splint attached to his broken arm provides a direct example of Roman orthopedic medical practice (Capasso 2001). Finally, although ancient Rome had various medical specialties, there was no distinct field dedicated to surgical orthopedics. Most procedures recommended by ancient authors would today be considered nonsurgical or conservative. When surgery was required, it was performed exclusively by a *Medicus Chirurgus* (surgeon), who likely received advanced training at medical schools in Roman provinces, such as Egypt or Greece (Belfiglio 2023).

In Late Antiquity, medicine extended well beyond state institutions, where it was preserved, refined, and further developed. The decline of the army and state apparatus in the West led to the disappearance of military hospitals (*valetudinaria*) by the fourth century C.E. This coincided with the emergence of civilian hospitals, such as xenodochia, evolving from

earlier hospices for the poor. These institutions played a crucial role in preserving medical practices after the collapse of the imperial system in the West (Martínez and González 2017). This helps explain the presence of medical texts aimed at nonprofessional audiences as early as the first century C.E. Knowledge transmission during this period relied on apprenticeship and written texts, including compilations. These works synthesized Roman medical literature, ensuring its influence extended into the Middle Ages (Van Minnen 1995). Written sources provide information on medical treatments from the later Longobard phase. Paul the Deacon's *Historia Langobardorum* (eighth century C.E.) mentions the practice of phlebotomy, or bloodletting, used to reduce King Grimoald's blood pressure (Pauli Diaconi, *Hist. Lang.*, liber V, cap. 33). Archaeological findings suggest that medical practitioners and their instruments were widespread in Late Antique and Early Medieval Italy, as evidenced by Roman (Gazzaniga and Marinozzi 2014) and Longobard cultures (Micarelli 2020). Additionally, until the sixth to seventh centuries C.E., some specialist professionals, such as metallurgists, were partly itinerant, serving a broad community and moving within a medium or small range (La Salvia 2019). The migration of technical knowledge in metallurgy and the fire arts can likely be applied to practitioners and individuals in medicine as well. Moreover, as observed in common medical practices, medical knowledge was preserved after the collapse of the imperial system through folk medicine, which reflected shared healing traditions. For instance, folk medicine helped perpetuate Galenic principles and botanical knowledge, bridging the gap between elite and popular medical practices (Martínez and González 2017:49).

Contextualizing the case study: the site of Selvicciola

The site includes a Roman *villa rustica* (countryside villa) and a cemetery located near the town of Viterbo, in Central Italy, 120 km northeast of Rome (Fig. 1A). In the infills dated to the third century C.E., likely attributable to the construction phases when the villa was equipped with an aqueduct, seals with rectangular cartouches bearing the inscriptions MINUCIUS C.F. and MINUCI were recovered. These likely indicate the *gens* or family who owned the residential complex. This helps chronologically frame the productive villa between the second century B.C.E. to the beginning of the fifth century C.E., when the villa was abandoned (Gazzetti 1995).

The funerary area close to the villa is dated between the beginning of the fourth and eighth

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Figure 1. (A) Location of Selvicciola archaeological area. (B) Map of the *villa rustica* and, in the gray framed square, the funerary area during the Longobard phase (Gazzetti 2005, modified). (C) The funerary area updated in its extension of burials; T90/5 in the red circle (Micarelli 2020, modified). (D) Plan of burial T90/5, showing a tomb with a travertine limestone coffin.

centuries C.E. (Fig. 1B). Two different cultural horizons of the cemetery were defined (Micarelli 2020): (1) an early phase between the late fourth and early seventh centuries C.E., which corresponds to the Roman and post-classical occupation, and (2) a second phase dated from the mid-seventh to early eighth centuries C.E., characterized by the Longobard occupation and cemetery use (Fig. 1C). During this time, the villa's buildings fell into disrepair and eventually were abandoned and left in a state of general ruin. However, evidence suggests that a community remained in Selvicciola. This occupation is demonstrated by post holes found in the *cocciopesto* floors of the thermal baths, marks from other fixtures on the travertine base in the peristyle area, and olive oil press basins in the atrium. These findings suggest that portions of the *villa* were repurposed for habitation, with huts, characteristic of the Longobard phase in Italy, constructed within the existing ruins (Gazzetti 1995). Written records for this area come from Gregory the Great's *Registrum Gregorii*, which recounts the first siege of the Longobard at Sovana, about 40 km northeast of Selvicciola, as well as the subsequent siege of Rome by Agilulf in the summer of 592. Despite the Byzantine reconquest of several centers in upper Lazio and lower Umbria, this entire

region fell under the Longobards' dominion in the early seventh century C.E. (Stasolla 2019). Thus, the Selvicciola area was under the Longobard domination without warfare-related activities.

There are 100 graves with 110 individuals recovered, comprising 73 adults (49 males, 20 females, four of indeterminate sex) and 37 non-adults (Manzi et al. 1995). Some graves were reopened for new depositions (Incitti 1997). The topographical development of the burial area reveals two distinct systems: one involving the inside of the church and the southern part of the necropolis (first phase; late fourth to early seventh centuries C.E., corresponding to the Roman and post-classical occupation) and the other organized around the church's presence. Outside, near the western edge, two burial groups are identified, dating to the second phase (mid-seventh to early eighth centuries C.E.), corresponding to the Longobard phase. The first group is located near the apse, with male graves containing only armed individuals with typical Longobard grave goods. In contrast, female graves lack accompanying objects, possibly reflecting a scarcity of ornaments or non-Longobard origins. These graves likely represent a group related to the Longobard culture buried in a distinct part of the necropolis. The second group comprises some

tombs east of the church, where abandoned buildings date back to the villa's construction during the Augustan phase (until the end of the second century C.E.; Gazzetti 2005). While many of these burials lack grave goods, only two male burials are in stone coffins (Fig. 1C, which are T90/5 and T90/6).

Tafari et al. (2018) show the tight clustering of stable carbon and nitrogen isotopic values measured in the bone collagen, indicating an unvarying diet, especially regarding protein intake. On the other hand, Manzi et al. (1995), through caries and enamel hypoplasia frequencies, showed a high consumption of grains and a low intake of meat for most individuals from the site. Additionally, Salvadei and colleagues (2001) found a correlation between osteological lesions (*cribra orbitalia*, porotic hyperostosis, and thin cortical bone) and grain intake, indicating a poor diet (see Walker et al. 2009). The lack of key dietary elements (iron, vitamin C or B3, protein, or calcium), caused by epidemics, famines, and political and administrative weakening, was common after the collapse of the Roman Empire (Killgrove 2017a, 2017b; Brickley and Ives 2020).

The Selvicciola necropolis thus represents a complex community, initially involving individuals from the villa's productive period, those who remained during its abandonment, and a group buried with Longobard grave goods. This phased division reveals differing living conditions between genders and individuals of different social roles within the same phase. The individuals buried in this funerary area were mainly farmers during the Roman phase. Later, it appears that the community became a strategic center used to control the region's productivity during the Longobard phase (Micarelli 2020).

The focus of this investigation is the individual labeled T90/5. The ¹⁴C dating revealed that T90/5 (lab code: FTMC-UT49-3) has a radiocarbon date of 1523 ± 29 B.P. (calCurves IntCal20), corresponding to a 435–635 cal. C.E. (95.4%) or 540–596 cal. C.E. (68.3%). Therefore, this individual can be placed at the end of the cemetery's first phase. Considering the first interval, this historical period coincides with the first arrival of the Longobards in northern Italy (568 C.E.).

Materials and Methods

Macroscopic examination

The individual under investigation (T90/5; Fig. 1C, D) was recovered from a tomb with a travertine limestone coffin. The skeleton inside the coffin was in excellent condition; the bones were intact, and 90% of the skeletal remains were preserved. Sex and age at

death were assessed by observing morphological traits of the skull and the pelvis (Brooks and Suchey 1990; Buikstra and Ubelaker 1994; Lovejoy et al. 1985; Phenice 1969). To compare results with contexts dated to the same period, stature was calculated by measuring the long bones and using methods present in bioarchaeological literature for Late Antique and Early Middle Ages skeletal collections from Italy (Bach 1965; Manouvrier 1892; Sjøvold 1952).

As part of the life history reconstruction of T90/5, a macroscopic pathological assessment was conducted on the entire skeleton, following methods outlined by Reid and Dean (2006) for enamel hypoplasia, Zampetti et al. (2016) for degenerative joint disease (DJD), and Mariotti et al. (2007) for enthesal changes. Dental lesions were examined using approaches synthesized by Buikstra and Ubelaker (1994). The assessment for traumas was conducted following Lovell (1997) and Redfern and Roberts (2019). Specifically, lesions related to the injuries were examined and recorded as (1) healed injury, the presence of compact bone callus, and (2) healing injury (*sensu* Mant 2019). To explore potential patterns of violent behavior, the method for assessing violence-related injuries (VRIs) was employed, following Brickley and Smith (2006). The paleopathological terminology used in this article aligns with the standards set by Buikstra et al. (2017).

Results

Macroscopic examination

The skeleton of T90/5 was estimated to be a male over 50 years old based on the morphological traits of the skull and the pelvis. Linear enamel hypoplasia observed in two anterior mandibular teeth (RII and LII) reveals at least two periods of interrupted growth occurring by the age of 2.

During his life, T90/5 suffered dental diseases (i.e., extreme wear and antemortem tooth loss [AMTL]). AMTLs are recorded as follows:

- Maxilla right side: AMTL: premolars and molars; left side: AMTL medial incisor tooth, second premolar and the molars
- Mandible left side: molars

The estimated stature, calculated as an average of the cited methods, is 165.5 cm (left side: maximum length humerus 32.0 cm and physiological length 31.6 cm, maximum length tibia 35.8 cm and physiological length 34.5 cm; right side: maximum length humerus 32.5 cm and physiological length 32.2 cm, maximum

length femur 44.5 cm and physiological length 43.7 cm, maximum length tibia 35.4 cm and physiological length 34.6 cm). As Salvadei et al. (2001) reported, micro-porotic lesions on the exterior surface of the skull *cribra cranii* were widespread in the population buried at Selvicciola. However, T90/05 does not show lesions related to hyperostosis or *cribra orbitalia*.

Evidence of pathology: description and interpretation

The paleopathological assessment shows multiple injuries, and the observation of different stages of healing in the injuries suggested a closer examination of injury recidivism (see Mant 2019). Table 1 describes the injuries on the skull, scapular girdle, and left femur, while Table 2 reports the injuries on the ribs. These injuries combine healed and healing trauma (Fig. 2). The timing of the healing process and the presence of bone callus differ. However, all the injuries can be classified as antemortem (Lovell 1997).

The skull

The left parietal exhibits one healed blunt-force trauma, measuring 2 cm at its longest point and having an oval shape (Fig. 3A–C). The defect can be classified as a pond fracture resulting from a low-velocity

blow that compressed the skull (see Kranioti 2015). The healing process is well advanced, as shown by the parietal bone's porous external surface. Additionally, a healed fracture is present on the right nasal bone. As shown in Figure 3D, the nasal bone fragments have healed but remain misaligned. This can be categorized as a type IIA fracture (fracture with displacement), according to Hwang et al. (2006), likely caused by a facial injury.

Scapular girdle

The right clavicle presents a well-healed fracture with the broken clavicle shafts overlapping. As a result, there is a considerable shortening of the bone. At the fracture point, there are two well-formed bony spurs. The shortening of the right clavicle shaft is well visible in Figures 4A, B. The acromion process of the left scapula is completely separated from the scapula body, identified as an *os acromiale*, a developmental condition resulting from an accessory center of ossification of the acromion of the scapula (Fig. 4C; Lambert 2015). The comminuted fracture of the body of the right scapula is completely healed, with ossification of fragments and bony ridges (Fig. 4D). In clinical cases, associated injuries are often seen, especially in the spine, skull, and chest (Brickley and Smith 2006).

Figure 2. T90/5 skeleton and the set of traumata. On the left is the state of completion of the skeleton; the bones present are gray-colored. Red stars: fully healed injuries; blue: bone in healing process. On the right is a close-up of the state of preservation of the shoulder girdle and the ribcage; the bones present are gray-colored. Red stars: fully healed injuries; green stars: green stick (GS) ones; yellow stars: bone calluses.

Table 1. Description of the Traumas on the Skull, Scapular Girdle, and Left Femur (Fig. 2)

	Location	Number of Injuries	Type of lesion	Consequences	State of Healing	Fig. n.	Clinical Time for Healing	References
Skull	Parietal	1	Pond fracture by low-velocity blow	Depression in the area	Healed	3A, B and C	From months to years BoD = acquired: medium to long term, BoC = LT more than 3 months	Kranioti 2015; Bethard et al. 2021
	Nasals	1	Fracture with displacement	Misalignment of the bones	Healed	3D	BoD = acquired: medium to long term, BoC = MT more than 3 months for patients over 20 y.o.	Hwang et al. 2006; Mondin et al. 2005
Scapular girdle	Right clavicle	1	Midclavicular fracture with bone shortening	Misaligned ends of the fracture site (bony spurs) and shortening of the bone	Healed	4A, B	BoD = acquired: medium to long term, BoC = M/LT 37.54 ± 14.63 weeks for heavy work	Wedel and Galloway 2013; Stanley and Norris 1988; Schofer et al. 2009; Cole and Horazdovsky 2016
	Right scapula	1	Fractures of the body	Ossification of fragments and the presence of bony ridges	Healed	4D	BoD = acquired: medium to long term, BoC = LT	
Ribs	Left and right side	7	Fractures of the body	See Table 2	Healed	5	6 months for the chronic pain to end BoD = acquired: medium to long term, BoC = MT	Claydon et al. 2018
Left femur	Neck	1	Transcervical fracture	Femoral neck fracture Neck: a thin layer of bone apposition from healing Head: area of bone apposition from healing on the spongiosa	Healing	6	Minimum 18/24 months BoD = end of life, BoC = LT	Lein et al. 2011; Makridis et al. 2015; Ives et al. 2016; Yang et al. 2023

For the BoC: = MT is for 3 to 6 months (medium term), = LT is for >6 months (long term).

Table 2. Description of the Traumas on the Ribs (Fig. 2)

Ant	Right		State of Preservation	Rib	State of Preservation	Left		
	Lateral	Post				Ant	Lateral	Post
GS on the neck	None	GS 3/3 of the shaft	Entire	1st	Entire	None	None	GS 3/3 of the shaft
	None		Entire	2nd	Entire			
	GS 1/3 of the shaft		Entire	3rd	Entire			
	GS middle of the shaft	GS 3/3 of the shaft	Entire	4th	Taphonomic break in the shaft			
		Callus 2/3 of the shaft Fig. 4E	Entire	5th	Entire			
		GS middle of the shaft	Entire	6th	Entire			
GS on the neck Callus on the neck Callus on the neck	None	None	Taphonomic break in the shaft	7th	Not present	None	None	None
			Entire	8th	Entire			
			Entire	9th	Entire			
			Entire	10th	Entire			
			Not present	11th	Entire			
			Entire	12th	Entire			

Anterior = anterior portion of the rib; lateral = lateral portion of the rib; posterior = posterior portion of the rib; GS = green-stick injury.

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Figure 3. Healed trauma on the skull. (A) The pond fracture on the left parietal indicated by the yellow arrow and the dotted line. (B) CT scan of the posterior view of the skull. (C) CT scan of the lateral view of the skull showing the pond fracture by low velocity on the left parietal; the yellow arrows indicate the location of the trauma, and the dotted line shows its diagonal measurement. (D) Healed nasal bones after the trauma pointed with a red arrow.

Figure 4. Healed trauma on the shoulder girdle and bone callus on the fifth right rib. (A) Left and right clavulae. (B) X-rays of left and right clavulae. The right clavicle (on the right) shows a midclavicular fracture with bone shortening. (C) The left scapula with the trait known as *os acromiale*. (D) The right scapula with healed comminuted fracture of the body. (E) bone callus on the 2/3 of the fifth rib shaft.

Figure 5. Severe osteoarthritis on the wrists. (A) Distal epiphyses of the left arm. (B) The distal epiphyses of the right arm exhibit lipping along the edges, slightly altering the shape of the surface. The arrows highlight the severity of bone changes at the styloid process and the articular surface of the distal radius. (C, D) The alteration of the shape on both the trapezium and proximal epiphyses of the first metacarpals is visible. The areas in green circles indicate the presence of eburnation.

Ribs

Seven ribs on the right side of the upper, middle, and lower ribcage exhibit well-healed fractures (Fig. 2 and Table 2). Three right ribs display oval bone calluses, with the upper rib near the sternal end and the lower ones at the rib angle. Four other ribs show evidence of greenstick fractures (Redfern and Roberts 2019) on the right side: two upper ribs each have two fractures, one at the neck and one near the sternal end; one lower rib has trauma at the neck, while the other lower rib shows the fracture on the shaft near the sternal end. On the left side, two ribs also show greenstick fractures, all located in the posterior region.

Wrists

The distal epiphyses of the right radius and ulna show a severe degenerative joint disease compared to the left side (DJD; Fig. 5A, B; Waldron 2019). Following

Zampetti et al. (2016), both bones of the right side present a high degree of marginal lipping (ML = 3). In addition, on the surface of the radial distal epiphysis, a diffuse porosity is observed (PO = 2). The proximal articular surfaces of both first metacarpals show marginal lipping (ML = 3) and eburnation (EB = 3). The two trapezia exhibit an altered bone morphology. The distinguishable articular surface is the saddle-shaped articular surface for the base of the first metacarpal (right and left; Fig. 5C, D). Eburnation is visible on both the trapezium and the proximal epiphyses of the first metacarpals.

Femur neck

Following Ives et al. (2016), the femoral neck fracture can be classified as transcervical (Fig. 6A, B). As shown in Figure 6C, the thin layer of bone healing on the femoral neck indicates that the individual

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Figure 6. Trauma on the femoral neck. (A) Posterior view of the femoral neck. The solid arrow indicates postmortem damage with sharp edges and no bone response. (B) Close-up of the fracture in lateral view. The dotted square highlights a portion of the edges, showing the smoothing of the fractured bone margins with a slight deposit of woven bone. (C) The 20× magnification of the fracture in lateral view using a Dino-Lite. The dotted arrow indicates the smoothing of the fractured bone margins, while the rectangle highlights the smoothly rounded and slightly elevated bone apposition.

survived the trauma. Additionally, the healing processes within the spongiosa of the femoral head provide further evidence of survival. Since the initial signs of healing typically appear at least 10 to 20 days after an injury—the minimum time required for the bone to initiate an osteoblastic reaction (de Boer et al. 2012; Lein et al. 2011; Işcan and Steyn 2013; Makridis et al. 2015; Yang et al. 2023)—this individual likely survived the early stage of healing. More specifically, as outlined by de Boer et al. (2012) in their investigation of healing features visible in dry bone, Figure 6 shows smoothing of the bone apposition outline, suggesting a healing period of four to seven days postinjury, along with slight apposition of primary woven bone (characterized by its rounded and elevated appearance, visible in Fig. 6C). However, there is no evidence of the transition from primary woven bone to secondary lamellar bone, which occurs after approximately 14 days. This is the only skeleton fracture exhibiting signs of ongoing healing.

Discussion

Fractures represent a cumulative pathology that records an individual's exposure to fracture risks throughout their lifetime. These injuries provide

valuable insight into the various factors and incidents contributing to a person's overall health and vulnerability to fractures over the years (Glencross 2011). Without evidence from the archaeological context and paleopathological analysis, it is impossible to differentiate between multiple injuries in a single event and injuries in separate episodes. However, antemortem and perimortem traumas may enable the reconstruction of the relative sequence of fracture events (Mant 2019). Three aspects of this case warrant discussion: the causes of the multiple injuries, the timing of the injuries, and the care and medical knowledge associated with the implications for mobility impairment.

The causes of the multiple injuries

Reconstructing the behavioral implications of antemortem and perimortem injuries is a two-stage process (Lovell 1997; Walker 2001). To further interpret the T90/5 case, the mechanism that led to the trauma must first be considered, starting with the proximate causes. The trauma to the left parietal bone was caused by a low-velocity blow, resulting in a depression in the area (Kranioti 2015). A facial injury likely caused the displaced fracture of the nasals with bone misalignment (Hwang et al. 2006). These injuries

indicate that the individual was struck at least twice—once on the left parietal bone and once on the face. Given the high-impact nature of scapula fractures caused by blunt-object impact or the body striking a blunt surface, clinical literature correlates open clavicle fractures from blunt trauma with a 52% rate of head injuries and a 52.9% rate of rib-associated injuries (Cole 2002:81). In clinical literature, ribs fractures are associated with low-velocity falls (Bergeron et al. 2003). Additionally, osteoporosis-induced bone fragility increases the likelihood of rib fractures, even with minimal force applied to the thorax (Cunha and Cunha 2022). A plausible explanation for the femur neck injury is that it may have resulted from indirect trauma, such as a slip or a twisted ankle, which could have caused a fall from a standing position (see femoral neck trauma case study in Lovell 2016). Although osteoporosis was not specifically assessed in T90/5, it is worth mentioning that osteoporosis-related bone loss results in more fragile bones that are prone to fracture (i.e., proximal humerus, distal radius, proximal femur, and proximal tibia), mainly from low-energy impacts caused by falls and stumbles (Warden et al. 2024).

Then, to contextualize an injury, looking beyond its immediate causes and exploring its cultural context, is essential. This process, aiming to identify the injury's ultimate cause, requires examining intrinsic factors, like age and sex, and extrinsic ones, such as the physical and sociocultural environment (Lovell 1997). Notably, the Selvicciola site, identified as an agricultural center, likely influenced the types of injuries sustained and their treatment. Among the injury recidivists are individuals whose traumas suggest both intentional violence and accidental causes (Mant 2019).

In contemporary clinical practice, certain injuries, such as cranial vault fractures (Adams and Goliath 2023) and fractures of the maxillofacial region (Arpalahti et al. 2022), are frequently associated with interpersonal violence. Brickley and Smith (2006) applied the concept of violence-related injuries (VRIs) to investigate these dual causes further. Their research highlights how clinical assault patterns often involve fractures of the cranial vault when associated with trauma to the maxillofacial area (e.g., nasal bones). In this case, the presence of violent trauma is further supported by the healed injury on the left parietal bone, located near the “hat brim line,” which may indicate interpersonal violence (Guyomarc’h et al. 2010). Additionally, its position on the left side of the skull suggests that it was likely inflicted by a right-handed aggressor facing the individual (Knüsel and Smith 2013). Today, the most common causes of nasal injuries are slipping or falling (35%), violence

(26.5%), sports (17%), traffic accidents (15%), and work-related (6.5%) (Hwang et al. 2006). Rib fractures can result from various causes, including interpersonal violence (e.g., chest blows, assaults), accidents, or occupational hazards (Wedel and Galloway 2013).

Furthermore, when a person sustains a head injury that alters bone without causing death, brain damage is inevitable. Such neurological trauma can affect various functions (for example, speech, memory, vision, behavior, and motor control). Increased behavioral violence and the decline in motor control elevate the risk of repeated injuries due to diminished self-regulation and heightened reactions from others, leading to injury recidivism (Martin et al. 2010).

The man from T90/5 could also have been involved in agricultural tasks. These tasks may account for some of the accidental causes of the skull, scapular girdle, ribcage, and upper arm injuries. Judd and Roberts (1999) and Baker and Papalexandrou (2012) noted similarities between rural communities working in farm settings without modern machinery. Hip and lower limb fractures are generally associated with vehicular and occupational accidents (Wedel and Galloway 2013). Routine work activities may lead to falls from a calash, horse kicks, falls from a ladder or barn, and collisions with animals (Cogbill et al. 1991). Also, Purschwitz and Field (1990) highlighted that in small-scale initiatives, many elderly individuals continue to perform tasks that strain their bodies. Falling from or being kicked by a horse or cow can lead to the life-threatening breakdown of the femur neck (Spence 2016). Finally, hip and lower limb fractures are usually associated with vehicular and occupational accidents, with the most likely cause being indirect trauma (for example, a slip or twisted ankle; Lovell 2016). Interpersonal as well as accidental causes remain plausible explanations.

In conclusion, as a possible ultimate cause, the villa's abandonment during the second phase of the Selvicciola site suggests another scenario: this individual may have been caught in a building collapse. In the early seventh century C.E., a modest settlement was established on the villa's ruins. The head trauma, fractures to the maxillofacial bones (including the nasal bones), and ribcage injuries (with fractures along the right posterolateral side, two ribs showing distinct fractures) may align with the injury patterns related to a possible building collapse (Dalkiran et al. 2013; Osterholtz et al. 2021).

The timing of the injuries

Individuals with multiple injuries are usually males, who typically sustain their first injury by age 20 and a second by age 30 (Martin et al. 2010 and cited

literature). Excluding the neck femur fracture, which shows a different stage of healing, there are two possible scenarios for the T90/5 case:

1. **Sequentially acquired injuries:** following an initial incident, additional injuries were sustained over time during subsequent events. One possible interpretation is that the initial episode involved cranial defects affecting the parietal and nasal bones. Over time, fractures to the scapular girdle and ribcage were incurred during later/combined incidents. This pattern of accumulating injuries after a significant prior trauma has led to the identification of T90/5 as a case of injury recidivism, even before the femoral neck fracture occurred.
2. **Skull, scapular girdle, and ribcage injuries as if acquired simultaneously:** a sole incident causes the set of injuries. The healing process of all affected bones in the right and left scapular girdle was complete before T90/5's death. As highlighted earlier, clinical literature associates blunt trauma of the clavicle to the head and ribcage injuries. This scenario of a significant prior event involving multiple injuries has led to the identification of T90/5 as a case of injury recidivism following the femoral neck fracture.

Finally, the femoral neck fracture is the only injury showing evidence of ongoing healing. This suggests that this individual likely only survived the initial stages of healing.

5.3 The care and the medical knowledge associated with the implications for mobility impairment

Clinical evidence strongly supports the medical treatment model described in “Background to medical knowledge of orthopedic treatments in classical and post-classical times.” Following the two timing scenarios of the injuries, the models of clinical impacts and care can be provided:

1. **Sequentially acquired injuries** (Fig. 7)
2. **Skull, scapular girdle, and ribcage injuries as if acquired simultaneously** (Fig. 8)

After sustaining blunt-force trauma to the left parietal region, the individual likely experienced a loss or alteration of consciousness. Such an injury could also lead to hemorrhaging (Chenoweth et al. 2018; De Leeuw et al. 2013). If the bleeding persisted, intraparenchymal pressure might have caused an epidural or subdural hematoma. In a case study on severe blunt-force trauma to the same area, Bethard et al. (2021) noted that this type of injury can impair memory, taste, and language production. Additionally, rib fractures can lead to serious complications, such as hemothorax and pneumothorax (Brickley 2006). In elderly patients, they are the most common injury associated with blunt-force trauma to the chest. With each additional rib fracture, the risk of developing pneumonia increases by 27% (Mant 2019:15 and cited literature). Additionally, rib fractures cause significant

Clinical impacts: sequentially acquired injuries		Model of care: sequentially acquired injuries
Short term:	S	Short - medium term:
<u>Probable</u> – Pain, shock, nausea, weakness, dizziness	K	- Personal hygiene, toileting, bathing, cleaning of the wounds
<u>Possible</u> – Severe shock, hemorrhage	U	- Bandaging
Medium term:	L	- Close monitoring for infections
<u>Probable</u> – Reduced mobility	L	- Psychological support
<u>Possible</u> – Pain, psychological depression	L	
Longer term:		
<u>Probable</u> – neurological dysfunction		
<hr/>		
Short term:	S G	Short - medium term:
<u>Probable</u> – Pain, shock, nausea, weakness, dizziness	C I	- Adequate fluid and nutrition (potentially special diet)
<u>Possible</u> – Severe shock, hemorrhage, pleural problems	A R	- Personal hygiene, toileting, bathing, cleaning of the wounds
Medium term:	P D	- Bandaging and dressing
<u>Probable</u> – Reduced mobility and inability to move independently, loss of joint movement, depressed immune system, respiratory tract dysfunction	U L	- Movement / changing position
<u>Possible</u> – Pain, psychological depression	L E	- Massage
Longer term:	A	- Close monitoring for infections
<u>Probable</u> – no heavy work, abnormal posture	R	- Psychological support
<hr/>		
Short term:	R	Short - medium term:
<u>Probable</u> – Pain, nausea, weakness, dizziness	I	- Personal hygiene, toileting, bathing, cleaning of the wounds
Medium term:	B	- Bandaging
<u>Probable</u> – Reduced mobility	S	- Psychological support
<u>Possible</u> – Pain		

Figure 7. Model of care after the sequentially acquired injuries.

-1—
0—
+1—

<p>Clinical impacts: simultaneous injuries</p> <p>Short term: <u>Probable</u> – Pain, shock, nausea, weakness, dizziness <u>Possible</u> – Severe shock, hemorrhage, pleural problems</p> <p>Medium term: <u>Probable</u> – Reduced mobility and inability to move independently, loss of joint movement, depressed immune system, respiratory tract dysfunction <u>Possible</u> – Pain, psychological depression, neurological dysfunction</p> <p>Longer term: <u>Probable</u> – no heavy work, abnormal posture</p>	<p>Model of care: simultaneous injuries</p> <p>Short - medium term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequate fluid and nutrition (potentially special diet) - Personal hygiene, toileting, bathing, cleaning of the wounds - Bandaging and dressing - Movement / changing position - Massage - Close monitoring for infections - Psychological support <p>Longer term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make him participate in community life with activities (preparation of food, no too heavy agricultural activities, i.e. planting, caring for the children)
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Figure 8. Model of care after the simultaneous injuries.

<p>Clinical impacts: femur injury</p> <p>Short term: <u>Probable</u> – Pain, shock, nausea, weakness, dizziness, reduced mobility and inability to move independently, depressed immune system <u>Possible</u> – Severe shock, haemorrhage, pain, psychological depression</p>	<p>Model of care: femur injury</p> <p>Short term:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adequate fluid and nutrition (potentially special diet) - Personal hygiene, toileting, bathing - Movement / changing position - Massage - Psychological support
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Figure 9. Model of care after the femur neck fracture.

pain during daily activities like coughing or sneezing due to discomfort (Claydon et al. 2018). These are challenges that T90/5 may have faced, at least until the bleeding subsided.

The healed injuries demonstrate how medical procedures and care provided by community members contributed to the successful recovery of T90/5, even though there is no evidence of clavicle reduction. While Roman texts recommended this procedure for clavicle injuries, it was not strictly necessary, as fracture reduction was considered mandatory for humeral fractures. In contrast, today, clavicle reduction requires a surgical procedure (Webber et al. 2000). Proper bandaging, however, was essential in all cases (Brorson 2009). According to Galen in his *De fasciis*, bandages had to be changed daily, and honey was applied until recovery. The preferred bandage for fractures of the humeral neck, as well as for shoulder dislocations and clavicle fractures, was the *spica simplex* (Brorson 2009).

After the femur neck trauma, T90/5 died likely within weeks, during which the care was ensured (Fig. 9). As already stated, for cases of disabled individuals from the past, not all patients can be cured, but there are no patients who cannot be cared for (Micarelli et al. 2024). In Roman times, to facilitate surgical procedures, patients were probably given powdered analgesics to induce twilight sleep before surgery. Procedures were performed as swiftly as possible, with powdered opium (*Papaver somniferum*)

in wine being the preferred analgesic. Other anesthetics mixed with wine included powdered mandrake (*Mandragora officinarum*, found in Italy) and powdered corn poppy (*Papaver rhoeas*). Following these treatments, patients typically experienced catalepsy, amnesia, and significant pain relief (Belfiglio 2018). Therefore, it is plausible to infer that, as part of the medical treatment provided, the individual was given analgesics to induce significant pain relief and possibly twilight sleep. Additionally, massage therapy was often prescribed, particularly when the body needed to relax due to tension or contraction. The Greek physician Asclepiades, who practiced in Rome during the first century B.C.E., is often credited as the inventor of massage therapy (Iorio et al. 2018). To aid in the restoration of the body's vitality, massage therapy was considered useful for dispersing excess humors throughout the body and served as a supplementary treatment to nutrition. So, a proper diet was also likely an essential component of the individual's care regimen. The provision of food and water would have been administered by someone who always monitored the individual's needs, ensuring that he was well nourished and hydrated.

Moreover, emotional support would have played a crucial role in his well-being, with a carer providing companionship and assistance with his daily needs. Indeed, the consequences of posttraumatic stress must also be considered in this case. New research in clinical and epidemiological medicine identified a link between

stress disorders after traumas and a higher risk of fractures (e.g., in the femur; Jiang et al. 2019), indicating a connection between psychosocial factors and increasing frailty in older adults (Möller et al. 2009; Pedersen et al. 2016; Yu et al. 2012). The potential impact of stress disorders at a psychosocial level must also be considered part of the embodiment of trauma for T90/5.

From the perspective of written sources, the community of Selvicciola remains undocumented. After the abandonment of the productive villa, the site appears to have functioned solely as a dwelling for a small residual community. While the specific cause of these injuries remains unknown, warfare can be excluded as a possibility based on the historical context. Nevertheless, it can be inferred that the knowledge gained from medical treatments in wartime scenarios could still be applicable in providing care to individuals in other contexts.

Osteobiography

In this section, the osteobiographical events of T90/5 are presented. Where possible, these events have been arranged in chronological order over the individual's life course, following examples found in the literature (e.g., Boutin 2016, 2022).

1. Despite childhood stress, as evidenced by the two periods of interrupted growth occurring by the age of two, he survived childhood and reached a mature age. His stature is comparable to that of the post-classical population in Italy (165.5 cm; Baldoni et al. 2019; Formicola e Holt 2007; Paine et al. 2009). However, T90/5's stature is lower than the average stature of the Italian population in the Late Antique population (169.5 cm; Bedini and Bertoldi 2004; Belcastro and Facchini 2001; Micarelli 2020).
2. The loss of teeth likely occurred over an extended period, influenced by various factors, including aging, genetic predispositions, trauma, poor oral hygiene (Kinaston et al. 2019), and a high consumption of grains. The latter is supported by biomolecular dietary analyses (Tafari et al. 2018: 499, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -19.19 , $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ 9.33; these values are typical for the average Selvicciola population). This isotopic analysis was performed on a rib fragment, which, due to its high turnover rate, is expected to reflect dietary inputs from two to 10 years before death. However, recent research indicates that rib bone samples can also represent dietary inputs from many

years before death (Quinn 2024). Notably, the absence of *cribra orbitalia* and *cribra cranii* lesions suggests the man maintained a balanced diet, implying that the community likely attended to him after the injuries and ensured his nutritional needs were met.

3. The man experienced several traumas, and the healing processes were evident in his bones (acquired: medium to long term; *BoD*). The community's model of care proved to be effective not only in the short term but also in the long term (more than six months; *BoC*). This care guaranteed his survival. During the man's recovery, the rural community in Selvicciola had to cope without the hard work of an active member for several months (at least 12 months, see Table 1). In the small community of Selvicciola, a well-organized care model was in place, ensuring that treatment and support were thoughtfully structured around individual's needs. The community played a significant role in health care, with members likely taking on different responsibilities during the medical treatment of T90/5, depending on their relationship with him. During the initial stages of his treatment, his relatives may have been particularly instrumental in ensuring he received the necessary medical attention and provided him with food and water during his recovery.
4. After the rehabilitation, people would likely have been sympathetic and assigned him tasks adapted to his lasting impairments. A computed tomography scan analysis was performed on this individual to evaluate the lateralization of cortical bone distribution along the diaphyses of the right and left humeri (methodology, Profico et al. 2021; outcome as part of a Ph.D. thesis, Zeppilli 2024). This individual showed a statistically significant difference in the deltoid and brachioradialis muscle attachment areas between the two humeri (Zeppilli 2024). Using the morphomap R package, the humeri were segmented, mirrored, and aligned, and their biomechanical lengths were calculated (following Ruff 2002). The lateralization index ($\text{JLAT}\% = 1.79$) indicated slight right-side lateralization, suggesting the individual retained functional mobility in the right upper limb (Zeppilli 2024). Given the extensive eburnation in his wrists and shortening of the right clavicle, we can infer two possible scenarios: (1) he may have engaged in non-heavy, low-impact, but repetitive biomechanical tasks, such as

- preparing food, light agricultural activities (e.g., planting), caring for children, or educational tasks like practicing crafts or processing leather, or (2) this individual may have continued to perform heavy tasks despite the potential impairment.
5. After the femoral neck trauma, he spent the final period of his life (*sensu* Bohling et al. 2022) lying in bed. Nowadays, for a successful recovery, 90% of hip fractures undergo surgery (Kaffashian et al. 2011). After the injury, he was assisted when possibly struggling to change position. During the end-of-life period, family and community members likely provided meals, personal hygiene, changing positions, massage, and psychological support (e.g., Iorio et al. 2018). It is reasonable to deduce that care strategies likely served a dual purpose: assisting the individual in adapting to his altered abilities while simultaneously offering psychological support and motivation to confront the latest challenges in his life course. Psychological effects may have been shaped by feelings of anger or frustration regarding repeated health setbacks, which could influence body image, self-confidence, and attitudes toward caregivers. As highlighted in the literature, trauma can significantly impact mental health (an example from a Gaelic Medieval context, McKenzie et al. 2022) and may also extend to aspects of sexuality (Tellier and Calleja 2017). Potential consequences include depression, social withdrawal, and heightened anxiety, mainly when traumatic experiences recur, interspersed with periods of immobility.
 6. At the time of his death, not only was there evidence of care provided by the community, but his social role within Selvicciola was also apparent. Like other contemporaneous burials, T90/5 was without grave goods, a practice common in post-classical and later Christian cemeteries (Barbiera 2013; Fiocchi-Nicolai 2003; Testini 1980). T90/5, an older adult, and T90/6, a young adult, were the only ones buried in a stone coffin in the entire necropolis. Both burials are located east of the church, among abandoned buildings, and belong to male individuals. Given the presence of a stone coffin, it can be argued that T90/5, with this small group of burials (Fig. 1C; T90/1, T90/4, T90/5, T90/6, T90/7, T90/9), represented a social group of some importance within the Selvicciola community at the time of the Longobards' arrival in Italy. The other burials near T90/5 are of

females (T90/7 and T90/4, this last one a female buried with Longobard artifacts) and subadults (T90/1, T90/9). Giostra (2017) presented evidence of diverse models for organizing burial spaces, typically centered on extended family groups during the first Longobard phase in Italy. The composition and degree of social differentiation within these burial groups varied across different sites. In some cases, there is evidence of individual mobility, particularly among women, likely due to exogamy. These funerary practices may have influenced the burial customs in the Selvicciola area as well. From this perspective, one can speculate about a complex interaction and negotiation between the Longobards buried in the group close to the apse and the local inhabitants of Selvicciola, where T90/5 may have played a significant social role. This phenomenon likely illustrates a blending of cultures and social integration between the Longobards and the local population at Selvicciola.

Conclusions

The osteobiographical investigation of this man from Selvicciola provided a unique opportunity to explore different paths of care and recovery in a case of injury recidivism. Such cases are rare in the bioarchaeological record, and this study contributes significantly to understanding past traumas and their healing processes. The archaeological examination of the necropolis and further contextualization of the burial underscore this individual's role within the community. Even in cases of repeated injury, a member is not left to face challenges alone; the community's support is mobilized multiple times if necessary. By integrating archaeological, ¹⁴C dating, isotopic, and osteological evidence, aspects of his social identity are reconstructed, offering deeper insights than palaeopathological studies alone could provide. An osteobiography of his life has been pieced together from various skeletal anomalies, and further analyses of mobility (isotope) and ancestry (ancient DNA) will broaden our understanding of the sociopolitical dynamics within this community.

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The X-rays of the clavicles and rib in Figure 4 were performed at the Centro Veterinario Valmarecchia (Rimini, Italy) using a Morpheus EVO E-100R HF-X22C. The computed tomography scans of the skull and the study of cortical bone distribution along the diaphyses performed by Carlotta Zeppilli were conducted at the Department of Radiological, Oncological, and Anatomic-Pathological Sciences, Sapienza University of Rome, using a Toshiba Aquilion 16-layer scanner with a slice resolution of 1.25 mm, an interslice distance of 0.62 mm, 120 KVp, and 80 mAs. I sincerely thank the laboratory teams that supported this research.

Ethical Statement

Ethical considerations were thoroughly addressed throughout the research, and no destructive analyses were conducted. The isotopic measurements are disclosed and available in Tafuri et al. (2018, Table 1, p. 499). The radiocarbon dating was performed at the Vilnius Radiocarbon Laboratory as part of an ongoing collaboration between the Laboratory of Palaeoanthropology and Bioarchaeology, Department of Environmental Biology at Sapienza University of Rome and the Joukowsky Institute at Brown University. The sample, a fragmented metatarsal bone from the T90/5 skeleton, was analyzed in compliance with Italian and international ethical and legal guidelines.

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